

Quantum Uncertainty Principles and Classical Statistical Mechanics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. April 28, 2022

Heisenberg's uncertainty principle for position-momentum $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ is considered as an important statement regarding quantum mechanics i.e. one cannot know both p and x exactly. Δx and Δp stand out because in classical mechanics one has an exact p and x at each t . Mathematically, however, Δx and Δp are standard deviations which may also be calculated in classical statistical mechanics, for example with the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. In particular, if one considers the ground state of a simple harmonic oscillator, the quantum $P(x)$ proportional to $\exp(-px/a)$ and $P(p)$ proportional to $\exp(-xxa)$ match the classical statistical probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ for a fixed value of T proportional to $\sqrt{k/m}$ where k is the spring constant. Thus for this special T , $\Delta x \Delta p$ for a classical statistical mechanical gas is identical to $\Delta x \Delta p$ for the ground state quantum oscillator. The probability is normalized the same way for both. The physics of the two situations, however, is completely different. Thus the Heisenberg uncertainty principle does not necessarily describe quantum mechanical behaviour alone.

If one uses entropic uncertainty, i.e. $S_p + S_x$ where S is Shannon's entropy, once again one uses $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$ and $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In principle, one could also calculate such an entropy for a classical gas i.e. use $P(x)P(p)$ in Shannon's entropy. The result $S_p + S_x$ does not imply one does not know about p if one knows x i.e. the usual quantum statement.

Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle

Quantum mechanics seems to be based on a wavefunction $W(x) = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. In other words a free particle is described by $\exp(ipx)$ and a bound particle by an ensemble $W(x)$. One may, however, create classical type probabilities $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$. If one knows p with full certainty then x is said to be completely uncertain.

The Heisenberg uncertainty principle may be derived by considering the variances:

$$\text{Var}(x) = \int dx W^*(x)W(x) x^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{Var}(p) = \int dp p^2 a^*(p)a(p) \quad ((1))$$

These variances, however, may also be calculated for a classical statistical gas. Thus the fact that the product $\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p)$ equals a certain value does not seem to prove one cannot know p with certainty and x with no certainty. In other words one may calculate $\text{Var}(x)\text{Var}(p)$ for both classical and quantum systems. It is only the classical mechanical case where one thinks of exact p and x values together.

In fact the form of the uncertainty relationship is based on Schwarz's inequality for vectors as shown in (1):

$$\langle f|f \rangle \langle g|g \rangle \geq \langle f|g \rangle \langle g|f \rangle \quad ((2))$$

Where $\langle f|f \rangle = \int dx (xW^*(x)) (xW(x))$, $\langle g|g \rangle = \int dp (a^*(p)p) (a(p)p)$ and

$\langle f|g \rangle =$ an inner product of $(xW^*(x))$ with $(p a(p))$ This is difficult to define as one has two different variables, but in quantum mechanics one may use the relationship $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$. Thus one may introduce $g(x) = -i\hbar/dx W(x)$ as shown in (1) and $\langle f|g \rangle$ is computable. Thus the limit $\hbar/2$ is of a quantum mechanical nature, but yields a lower bound for the product of two quantum variances. Classical statistical variances may be computed and multiplied together even though they describe a very different physical scenario..

Ground State Harmonic Oscillator

The quantum ground state oscillator is interesting because it yields:

$$P(x) = W(x)W(x) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-Axx) \text{ and } P(p) = a(p)a(p) \text{ proportional to } \exp(-pp/A) \quad ((3))$$

Where A is proportional to \sqrt{km} , k being the spring constant i.e. $A = b \sqrt{km}$.

For a classical statistical mechanical system:

$$P(x) \text{ is proportional to } \exp(-pp/2mT) \text{ and } P(p) \text{ is proportional to } \exp(-.5kxx/T) \quad ((4))$$

For the quantum case, one normalizes $\int P(x)P(p) dx dp = 1$ and for the classical $\int P(x)P(p) dx dp = N =$ the number of particles.

It is possible to find a special value of T such that the quantum and classical probabilities distributions are identical i.e.

$$A = 1/(2mT) \text{ and } 1/A = k/(2T) \text{ or } T = .5 \sqrt{k/m} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one may have the same $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ for a quantum and classical statistical scenario even though the physics of both are very different. For the classical gas the statistical driver is stochastic two body collisions which enforce a constant average T at each x. This leads to a certain pressure which must adjust to match the force $-dV(x)/dx$. Thus the physical density must vary at each x i.e. there are different numbers of particles at different x values.

It is interesting to note that for a classical gas with a potential $V(x)$, one may consider a single particle. If one knows it is at position x, one does not know its momentum i.e. there is a distribution of $P(p)$. If one knows the particle has a momentum p, it may be at any x with $P(x)$. Thus there is a similar idea to quantum mechanics at work even in the classical example. The comparison, however, is not identical because for a gas in a box with no potential, the single particle has $P(p)$ if it is at x, but if one chooses a fixed p, it may be at any x with the same probability which is not the quantum scenario. One may note that a quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls also has a $P(p)$, it is only pave which is a constant.

As a result, it seems that $\Delta x \Delta p$ is not a particularly quantum measure.

Entropic Uncertainty

Attempts have been made to find stricter uncertainty principles than the Heisenberg one. In particular entropic uncertainty (2) is given by:

$$H(x) + H(p) \geq \log(e/2) \quad ((6)) \text{ where } H \text{ is Shannon's entropy}$$

Shannon's entropy, however, is calculated using classical-like probabilities $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ so it too may be calculated using classical statistical mechanical probabilities although the RHS limit of ((6)) will not apply.

The point seems to be that one calculates classical like quantities e.g. $\text{Var}(x)$, $\text{Var}(p)$ or $H(x)$, $H(p)$ for a quantum system. In such a case, the quantum features are linked to the fact that $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ i.e. there is a very specific relationship between $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p) = a^*(p)a(p)$. The expression $H(x) + H(p)$, however, may be constructed from P (Shannon) = $P(x)P(p)$ which is completely classical because in quantum mechanics one does not know x and p exactly at the same time. As a result, the form $H(x) + H(p)$ is as relevant in quantum mechanics as it is in classical statistical mechanics.

The issue seems to be that classical probabilities $P(p)$ and $P(x)$ exist in quantum mechanics and are measurable, but quantum mechanics is ultimately based on $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ which begs the question: Could one have meaningful statistical uncertainty relationships based only on $W(x)$ and $a(p)$ which do not involve their moduli?

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue that the Heisenberg momentum- x uncertainty principle $\Delta x \Delta p \geq \hbar/2$ where Δ is standard deviation is usually taken as a signature of quantum behaviour because in classical mechanics there is no uncertainty of x and p . In particular, in quantum mechanics one states that if one knows x exactly, one does not know anything about p . The calculation of variances, however, is strictly a mathematical process which uses $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ which are classical-like probabilities. Thus one may carry out the product $\Delta x \Delta p$ for a classical statistical gas. It is interesting to note that there is a kind of uncertainty even in such a gas because if one knows a single particle is at x , one has no idea of its momentum value i.e. it is described by $P(p)$. If one knows a single particle has a specific momentum p , it may be at any x with $P(x)$. Thus the quantum uncertainty scenario seems to exist to a certain degree in a classical gas. In particular, for the ground state of a quantum oscillator $P(x)$ and $P(p)$ classical gas are identical to $P(x)$, $P(p)$ quantum for a particular value of T . In such a case calculations of variances may not shed any light on whether the system is classical or quantum mechanical even though the physical properties of the two are very different.

Using entropic uncertainty instead of Heisenberg's uncertainty relationship does not seem to solve this issue because it too uses $P(x)$ and $P(p)$. In fact the form $S_p + S_x$ where S is Shannon's entropy is used in the entropic uncertainty relationship and it follows directly from a classical statistical system which uses $P(\text{Shannon}) = P(x)P(p)$ suggesting one may know p and x together.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncertainty_principle
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Entropic_uncertainty